

Acknowledgement

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Synthesis of Some 3-phenanthryl Keto-Anils

R. K. UPADHYAY

Department of Chemistry, N.R.E.C. College, Khurja-203131
&

SHYAM SUNDER MISRA*

Department of Chemistry,
Feroze Gandhi Post-Graduate College, Raebareli-229001

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THE anils have been synthesised by different workers¹⁻⁵ but those derived from glyoxals and aryl amines have not been investigated comprehensively. These compounds have been reported¹¹⁻¹⁴ to be chelating agents for various transition elements. Therefore, a systematic study in the preparation of 3-phenanthryl anils was undertaken.

In the present communication preparation of nineteen new 3-phenanthryl anils have been narrated (Table 1). These anils were prepared by refluxing the reactants in glacial acetic acid except those at sl. no. 14, 15, 16, 18 and 19. These compounds showed a typical behaviour finally giving a tarry

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF 3-PHENANTHRYL ANILS AND DERIVATIVES

Sl. no.	R	Colour and crystal form	Yield %	M.P.°C			λ_{max} Pri.	(nm) for	
				Anil	Oxime	Semi-carbazone		> C=O	> C=N Sec.
1.	H	L.B. plates	80	85	137	157	240	—	211
2.	2-CH ₃	G.Y. plates	83	138	113	135	267	293	222
3.	3-CH ₃	O. needles	75	131	123	147	268	295	221
4.	4-CH ₃	O. needles	86	140	133	152	267	294	221
5.	2-NO ₂	Y. plates	72	128	161	159	295	320	277
6.	3-NO ₂	Buff globules	76	103	120	146	297	321	267
7.	4-NO ₂	Y. plates	69	115	127	123	294	319	270
8.	2-OH	Grey needles	82	220	114	143	296	340	284
9.	3-OH	G.Y. needles	71	261D	205	198	280	297	267
10.	2-OCH ₃	G.Y. plates	84	103-4	111	151	296	314	271
11.	4-OCH ₃	O. globules	98	122	146	153	294	—	263
12.	2-Cl	Y. plates	60	91	101	118	295	316	269
13.	3-Cl	Y. needles	78	141	112D	127	296	—	267
14.	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	B. needles	77	79	197	126D	275	—	253
15.	5:6-benzo	B. globules	73	224	201	213	296	—	271
16.	3:4-benzo	Y. needles	75D	188	159	162	280	295	265
17.	OH-2:3-benzo-4-SO ₂ H	G. needles	81	95	116	—	294	317	277
18.	p-phenylenediamine	O. plates	93	—	—	—	—	345	257
19.	m-phenylenediamine	O. plates	89	208	136	143	270	292	258

L = light; B = brown; G = greenish; O = orange; Y = yellow; D = decompose.

* Postal Address: P.O. Bichwan, Dist. Mniapuri 205267.

mass without giving the desired product. The synthesis in ethanol medium resulted in a semi-solid mass, which on purification from acetone furnished crystalline products. These compounds are characterised by their physical properties, elemental analysis and oxime and semicarbazone derivative preparation. The anils and their derivatives were analysed satisfactorily for C, H, and N.

The absorption spectra of 3-phenanthryl anils were recorded in ultra-violet region on Beckmann G2400 DU Spectrophotometer in chloroform solution. The first band in the spectra, ranging from 211–284 nm, may be attributed to conjugated azomethine ($>C=N-$) group and second band from 240–297 nm, indicated⁹ the presence of conjugated carbonyl ($>C=O$) group. Another interesting band between 293–321 nm, may be regarded as secondary band of carbonyl group. The higher values may be due to substitution and conjugation in the nucleus. It is also observed that λ_{max} values for azomethine group in ortho substituted compounds is of higher value than those in para and meta-substituted compounds.

The infra-red absorption spectra of these anils were recorded on Infracord spectrophotometer. These spectra showed azomethine ($>C=N-$) absorption band between 1618–1633 cm^{-1} which is considerably lower than that of open chain compounds (1955–1943 cm^{-1}), probably due to conjugation or other side group effects.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected and recorded in an open capillary.

1. Preparation of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal

3-Acetyl phenanthrene¹⁰ (2.0 g) was treated with selenium dioxide (1.5–2.0 g) in 80% acetic acid at 100° and heating continued for 2 hr. The resulting yellow solution had characteristic glyoxalic odour and this on usual treatment, gave yellow amorphous product which was crystallised from acetone in the form of plates, m.p. 104°.

2. Synthesis of Anils

These were synthesised by the usual procedure. One typical example is cited below.

Equimolar quantities of 3-phenanthryl glyoxal and 2-chloro aniline were dissolved in glacial acetic acid and heated at 100° for 2 hr. The resulting solution on decomposition with water gave dark coloured crude product which was crystallised from chloroform (Table 1).

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Optically Active Aliphatic Esters from S-(+)-3-Methylcaproic Acid by Arndt-Eistert Synthesis

I. G. VASI & N. T. NANAVATI

Chemistry Department, University School of Sciences, Gujarat University, Ahmedabad-380009

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THE preparation and properties of a series of optically active esters of the type (VII) are described (cf. Fig. 1). Compounds (VII) were prepared from the acid chloride (V) through compound (VI) by Arndt-Eistert reaction^{1-3, 4-6}. (V) was prepared by the following known reaction steps: II → III → IV → V.

Figure 1

(I)R' = OH, (II) Br, (III) CH(COOEt)₂, (IV) CH₂COOH, (V) CH₂COCl, (VI) CH₂COCHN₂ (not isolated), (VII) CH₂CH₂COOR.

Experimental

S-(+)-3-Methylcaproic acid (IV)

S-(+)-2-Methyl-1-bromobutane (II)' (116 g) was condensed with sodium salt of ethyl malonate; prepared from sodium (19.8 g), absolute ethanol (350 ml) and diethylmalonate (126 g, 117 ml).